

A Multi-filter Fingerprint Matching Framework for Cancelable Template Design

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Abstract—Despite the ubiquity in the use of biometrics due to its many advantages against traditional methods such as password or token, the emerging cancelable biometric methods, which are designed to protect the biometrics are still exposed to certain threats. Attack via Record Multiplicity (ARM) is one of those. In this paper, we propose a novel framework that possesses two layers of authentication to improve the matching performance of a fingerprint authentication system in the cancelable template setting. In addition, a multi-filter fingerprint matching scheme is devised to deal more effectively with low-quality fingerprint images. Two techniques that are capable of defending against the heinous ARM are also introduced. Security analysis on the system’s capability against the hill-climb attack and pre-image attack is also provided. The proposed scheme has been evaluated over public datasets FVC2002-DB1, FVC2002-DB2, FVC2002-DB3, and FVC2004-DB2. It has achieved the best result compared with the state-of-art methods. The source code for this framework is available on demand.

Index Terms—Cancelable, biometrics, fingerprint, Multivariate Polynomial Equations System, binary representation, template protection

I. INTRODUCTION

THE fingerprint authentication system has been popular as it is capable of identifying and verifying people in many fields, such as: forensics, system authentication, human resource management, and so on. It is now one of the must-have features on a smartphone as it can address the problems of traditional password or token-based authentication schemes: One can forget the password or the token key can be lost or stolen. These are not applicable to fingerprint. However, if an adversary can retrieve the original fingerprint of a person, the victim is considered to have lost the fingerprint forever. More importantly, other applications that use the fingerprint for the authentication are exposed to a serious threat as well. Hence, it is crucial to protect the original fingerprint data from being compromised. Many fingerprint protection schemes have been devised to address this issue. Cancelable template is one of them.

Ratha et al. [1] proposed the concept of cancelable template in 2001 to protect the biometric authentication system. The idea is to transform the raw fingerprint features such that the compromised template cannot reveal the raw fingerprint features. As a result, a new transformed template can be generated using a different transformation key. This transformed template is stored in the database so that when a query comes, the same process is applied to generate a transformed version

of the query fingerprint. Matching is performed between two transformed fingerprints without the database storing the original features.

Biometric template protection can also be achieved with bio-cryptosystem techniques (biometric-related key binding and key generation) [2]–[4]. The main purpose of the bio-cryptosystem is to hide/extract the cryptographic key for the use in the subsequent cryptographic protocols. A hidden/extracted cryptographic key can be released after biometric matching. In some authentication-oriented applications such as access control of computers, and mobile devices where cryptographic key management is not an issue or even needed, cancelable biometric template-based matching can play an important role in providing privacy-preserving based authentication service. Using bio-cryptosystem (e.g., fuzzy extractor) for authentication-oriented applications such as access control will incur unnecessary data management overhead as it will need to store a helper data, the hash value of the secret, and involve the process of retrieving the secret, error correction and matching against the stored hash of the secret. In short, bio-cryptosystems focus on protecting the secret while cancelable biometric’s concern is privacy-preserving authentication.

A cancelable biometric design needs to satisfy the following characteristics [1]:

- **Revocability:** If a transformed template is compromised, a new template can be re-issued.
- **Diversity:** Templates generated by different keys from the same fingerprint should not have any correlation.
- **Non-invertibility:** Transformed templates cannot be reverted to the original biometric data even if the key is exposed. Note: in the standard ISO-24757, the terminology of irreversibility is used. Although non-invertibility terminology is widely used in the community, this terminology of non-invertibility is not consistent with the mathematical definition of irreversible function, which refers to the unique input/output mapping. To avoid the confusion, in the remaining of the paper, we will use the terminology irreversibility as defined in the standard ISO-24757.
- **Accuracy:** Matching performance should not significantly degrade after the transformation.

In this paper, we introduce an advanced framework in which two layers of authentication have been added to ensure the performance quality. It is also resistant to the Attack via Record Multiplicity (ARM).

The contributions of this paper are summarized as follows:

- 1) A novel irreversible cancelable module called Enhanced

Fig. 1: Multi-filter Fingerprint Matching Framework: A fingerprint’s raw information is fed to the two different feature extraction and transformation modules: the KNN-MPT module and the EMCC module. Their outputs will be given to the decision-making module: the Multi-layer Fingerprint Matching Algorithm.

Minutia Cylinder Code (EMCC) is proposed. The idea is to transform the real-valued MCC [5] into a bag of words based on the concept of natural language processing. Within each word, an irreversible order-based encoding process is applied to generate the irreversible cancelable feature, which is capable of defending against ARM.

- 2) An enhanced Local Similarity Sort (LSS) algorithm is proposed where a dynamic weight function is used to improve the performance.
- 3) Our proposed KNN Minutia Descriptor with non-linear Multivariate Polynomial Transformation module (KNN-MPT) is capable of defending against ARM.
- 4) Conventionally, a single matching threshold is used. In practice, it is hard to find such optimal fusion score for the single matching threshold while retaining all discriminative characteristics for all instances. Our proposed multi-layer matching algorithm can help address this issue.
- 5) Our proposed multi-filter fingerprint matching framework can integrate the advantages of the multi-filter (KNN-MPT and EMCC modules) and the multi-layer matching algorithm in achieving a better performance in terms of authentication accuracy and security of the overall system.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section II reviews some published works in the field. The proposed work is detailed in Section III whereas Section IV is dedicated to show the results of experiments. Security analysis is provided

in Section V. Finally, Section VI concludes the paper.

II. RELATED WORK

Ratha et al. [6] was one of the first works in cancelable template in which Cartesian Transformation, Polar Transformation, and Functional Transformation were proposed. Tulyakov et al. [7] proposed to represent minutiae in a fingerprint by a complex plane as a hashed set. Matching is performed between two hashed sets. Kumar et al. [8] improved this work by using more hash functions. However, the computational complexity is the disadvantage of this work. In 2008, Chikkerur et al. [9] proposed to construct another alignment-free template using localized texture features from the minutiae with a two-factor key method being used as the protection of the original features. Various attack modes were discussed but the lost key scenario was not mentioned.

Das et al. [10] proposed another work on alignment-free design for cancelable template by using a minimum distance graph hashing algorithm to construct a set of connected nodes by repeatedly calculating the distance between a core and its nearest minutia. The dependence of identifying the core points makes the performance of this method limited. In addition, the authors did not evaluate the algorithm with low-quality datasets such as FVC2002 DB3 or FVC2004 DB2. Yang et al. [11] used a dynamic random projection matrix to protect the raw feature. The novelty in this work is that the feature vectors themselves determine the selected projection vectors. However, once again, Yang et al. only evaluated the algorithm

with the finest quality dataset: FVC2002 DB2. Whether or not this scheme works with low-quality datasets is still an unanswered question.

Ahmad et al. [12] proposed a method based on the relative position between two minutiae in the pair coordinate system. This method works well on the good quality datasets but fails to work with low quality ones. Yang et al. [13] extracted local features using the Delaunay Triangulation method and used the Polar Transformation from [6] as the irreversible transformation. However, the performance of this method is poor.

Wang and Hu [14] used three-feature vectors to create binary string then transformed it into complex type vectors using the Discrete Fourier Transformation. Cancelable template is generated by using an infinite-to-one mapping. On top of that work, the work in [15] used another many-to-one mapping to transform the fingerprint to cancelable template. Another work proposed by Wang et al. [16] used a partial Hadamard as the irreversible transformation. Although it shows good performance with good-quality datasets, it suffers from the same degradation when dealing with the low-quality images. In the same year, Wang et al. [17] proposed a novel method to identify local structures from which the features were extracted. Partial Discrete Fourier was used as the irreversible transformation. Although this method achieved very competitive results, poor performance when dealing with poor quality datasets is still a weak point. In addition, these kinds of transformation degrade the performance. More importantly, these works are still vulnerable to the ARM.

In 2015, Sandhya and Prasad [18] proposed a kNN-based local structure cancelable template design in which the relative rotation and orientation were calculated and extracted to be represented by a binary string. The authors used a random matrix as a personal key to combine with the Discrete Fourier Transformation to create the irreversible transformation. On the other hand, the results in terms of EER (4.71% for FVC2002 DB1 and 3.44% for FVC2002 DB2) are too weak to show any feasibility. In 2018, Tran et al. [19] also proposed to use a kNN-based local structure with DFT being the protection layer. In their work, four features were extracted: line segment between a member and the reference minutia, the angle formed by the reference minutia's orientation vector and the line, the angle formed by the member minutia's orientation vector and the line, and the type of the member minutia. A bit string was also used as input for the transformation. However, this work applied the partial DFT that was proposed in [17]. Importantly, although it was claimed to limit the chance of being exploited by the ARM with short keylength, the results yet suffered from some degradation. Kho et al. [20] proposed a cancelable fingerprint design that extracts a Partial Local Structure Descriptor to combine with a user key for permutation in order to create a binary cancelable template. This work shows competitive matching performance compared with other state-of-art methods in the field. However, there still exists some tradeoff between security and performance. Sadhya et al. [21] utilized the Locality Sampled Codes to represent the features of a fingerprint in the binary form. A cancelable template is generated by sampling random bit

locations from the binary representation. The proposed method was evaluated with FVC2002 DB1, FVC2002 DB3, FVC2004 DB1, and FVC2004 DB2, yielding EERs of 0.19%, 1.44%, 1.28%, and 2.72%. However, the authors only used 1000 tests to evaluate the FRR. This makes the work hard to compare with other systems. Recently, Abdullahi et al. [22] proposed an alignment-free cancelable fingerprint design based on Fourier-Mellin transform and fractal coding to generate the hash value of each fingerprint, achieving good recognition performance when evaluated with FVC2002 and FVC2004 databases. However, with the low quality FVC2004 DB2, this method still shows a high EER (5.925%).

III. PROPOSED WORK

Given a set $M = \{m_1, m_2, \dots, m_n\}$ representing a fingerprint image that contains n minutiae, each minutia m_i is represented by $m = \{x_m, y_m, \theta_m, t_m\}$, where x_m and y_m are the coordinates of the minutia, θ_m is the minutia orientation in the range of $[0, 2\pi]$ and t_m is the minutia's type (ending or bifurcating minutia). Note that the minutia's type will only be used with the KNN minutia extractor. Therefore, we will not mention it in the MCC-related parts. Our proposed multi-filter fingerprint matching framework is illustrated in Fig. 1: In the enrolment phase, a fingerprint's minutiae raw information is fed to the two different feature extraction and transformation modules: the KNN-MPT module and the EMCC module. In the KNN-MPT module, the KNN Minutia Descriptor applies the k-nearest-neighbor clustering to select the minutia members of each local structure first; then each local structure's representative features are extracted. A quantization process is applied before the binarization and level. In order to create the cancelable template, a set of user-specific parameters is used to transform the binarized features with the Multivariate Polynomial Transformation (MPT). This transformed KNN Descriptor is stored in the database. On the other hand, the real-valued MCC vector is constructed based on the minutia information provided to the EMCC module. The user-specific random projection matrix is applied on this vector. Afterwards, bags of words are generated and then encoded into a binary representation. Next, this binary data is stored in the database along with the KNN Descriptor's transformed templates. To verify a fingerprint, the same process is applied to the query in generating the outputs of these two modules. The matching module generates three measures: the KNN-MPT measure, the EMCC measure, and the fused measure, which all are fed to the Multi-layer Fingerprint Matching Algorithm to make a decision.

A. Minutia Cylinder Code Concept

Minutia Cylinder Code (MCC) introduced by Cappelli et al. [5] in 2010 represents each minutia based on a 3D structure that contains information of relative minutiae's Euclidean distance and angle. This section briefly reviews the concept of creating the MCC for each minutia. More details can be found from the reference [5].

The cylinder of a minutia $m = \{x_m, y_m, \theta_m\}$ in the set M is constructed by setting m as the center associated with a

Fig. 2: Irreversible Order-based Encoding Process: A word consisting of two real-valued parts is encoded into a binary code based on their relative values.

radius R and the height 2π . The cylinder is wrapped around by a cuboid with the base being aligned with the minutia's orientation. The cuboid is divided equally into L_D layers. The total number of cells of each cylinder is: $L_S \times L_D = L_C$. Then, each layer is equally partitioned into L_S number of small cuboid cells. The value of the cell at the position (i, j, k) is determined by the directional and spatial contributions of the minutiae within its neighborhood.

In the end, the cylinder set generated from an ISO/IEC 19794-2 minutiae template is: $CS = \{C_m | C_m \text{ is valid, } m \in M\}$. Each C_m is the cylinder of the minutia m that contains values $C_m(i, j, k)$. In order for a cylinder C_m to be valid, it has to satisfy certain conditions. These conditions are presented in the original paper [5].

To summarize, an MCC vector contains the cell values ranging from $[0, 1]$, which are the spatial and directional contributions of the neighboring minutiae. In the next section, we will use the MCC cell values to derive new features for better matching.

B. EMCC

Algorithm 1: Generate Encoded Bag of Words

Data: Set of Cylinder CS , Number of Words Λ ,
Projection Matrix R_P

Result: Set of Bag of Words BS

foreach Vector C_m in CS **do**

 multiply R_P with C_m to get C_{mP} ;
 generate Λ words from C_{mP} to get Bag of Words

Γ_m ;

foreach word w in Γ_m **do**

 Binarize w orderly;

In this section, we will introduce a new method based on the concept of natural language processing. The idea is to transform each cylinder C_m in the Cylinder Set CS into a bag of words Γ_m . Within each word, an encoding process will be applied as an irreversible transformation. Therefore, the Cylinder Set CS becomes the Bag Set $BS = \{\Gamma_m | m \in T\}$, which will be stored in the database for matching. Pseudo code of this process is presented in Algorithm 1.

1) *Random Projection of C_m* : In order to generate cancelable template, we will first apply a random projection on the vector of MCC values. In details, a random *Projection Matrix*

R_P with dimension $d_R \times L_C$ is generated to project the C_m . Each R_P 's value lies in the range of $(0, 100]$.

$$C_{mP} = R_P * C_m \quad (1)$$

2) *Generation of Bag of Words*: After projecting the MCC value vector, a bag of words is generated from the C_{mP} . Each bag contains individual unit of words. Each word comprises of two adjacent cell values that are chosen from the cylinder. Such word construction can help retain the relationship among the cells, making the words more discriminative. We will generate Λ words for each bag. Λ is randomly chosen. After this process, each bag of word can be represented as: $\Gamma_m = \{w_1, w_2, \dots, w_\Lambda\}$ in which $w = (C_{mP}(i, j, k), C_{mP}(i', j', k'))$.

3) *Irreversible Order-based Encoding*: As we know, a random projection-based cancelable template design is subject to the ARM. We will protect each word (i.e. cell values) by applying an irreversible order-based encoding function as indicated in Fig. 2. Specifically, the two parts $C_{mP}(i, j, k)$ and $C_{mP}(i', j', k')$ of each word, which are MCC neighboring cells in real-valued form, will be compared against each other. The greater value yields bit '1' while the smaller yields bit '0'. If they are equal, then both yield '1'. Both values cannot be zero due to the fact that based on Eq. (1), C_m is non-negative and R_P is generated in a non-negative manner. The order-based encoding provides an irreversible transformation on the fingerprint features. If an adversary is able to retrieve the transformed template, which is in the binary form, he can only determine which part of a word yields a greater real number. There is no way to find out the original value. For instance, assume that $C_{mP}(i, j, k) = 0.95$ and $C_{mP}(i', j', k') = 0.62$. After the irreversible Order-based Encoding, this word is encoded as $[1, 0]$. There is an infinite number of words that can be encoded as $[1, 0]$.

Therefore, the Order-based Encoding will be applied to the C_{mP} as the irreversible transformation. On the other hand, the projection matrix is a parameterized transformation with random elements. Hence, in order to generate a new cancelable template, a different projection matrix R yields a different C_{mP} . In the end, the C_{mP} can be used as the cancelable fingerprint template to be stored in the database.

Next, each bag will be separated into small chunks with length of Φ words. The purpose of this separation is to enhance the tolerance of the bag of words by the localization of error tolerance at the chunk level, thus improving the overall performance. Therefore, each Bag of Word contains

$\lceil \frac{\Lambda}{\Phi} \rceil$ words and eventually becomes: $\Gamma_m = \{\gamma_1, \gamma_2, \dots, \gamma_{\lceil \frac{\Lambda}{\Phi} \rceil}\}$ in which each $\gamma = \{w_{b1}, w_{b2}, \dots, w_{b\Phi}\}$ and w_b is the two-bit encoded word. This is the transformed data which is stored in the database as the templates.

4) *Similarity between two Bag of Words*: To evaluate the similarity between two Bags of Words, we need to determine the similarity between two chunks. The similarity between two chunks is the Jaccard similarity calculated position-wisely, meaning that the chunk at i -th position in the template will be compared against its counterpart at the same position. Specifically, it is given in the following formula:

$$\delta_{\gamma_{ti}, \gamma_{qi}} = \frac{H(\gamma_{ti}, \gamma_{qi})}{2\Phi - H(\gamma_{ti}, \gamma_{qi})} \quad (2)$$

where $H(\gamma_{ti}, \gamma_{qi})$ is the Hamming distance between two chunks γ_{ti} and γ_{qi} , respectively. A word from template and a word from query are considered a match to each other if and only if each of their bits is the same to its counterpart position-wisely.

The similarity between two chunks is filtered by a parameter ϵ : Those pairs possessing passed similarity are considered as matched chunks. Counting the number of matched chunks (η) between two Bags of Words and using the Jaccard similarity, we are able to evaluate the similarity between two Bags of Words. Hence, Eq. (2) becomes:

$$\Delta_{\Gamma_m, \Gamma_n} = \frac{\eta}{2 \lceil \frac{\Lambda}{\Phi} \rceil - \eta} \quad (3)$$

After the similarity between all pairs of Bag of Words has been calculated, the next step is to determine the matching score S_{emcc} for this layer. We proposed a modified version of the Local Similarity Sort (LSS) from [5] to do this.

In the original version, LSS sorts all the similarity scores in a descending order and calculates the average score based on the n_P pairs chosen, which is partially dependent on the number of minutiae of the template and the query. In our scheme, this parameter is chosen based on the behavior of the scores. First, we will set a threshold ω_{bag} to filter the low similarity scores between two Bags of Words. Sorting is performed after this. The score values lower than ω_{bag} will be set to 0 after sorting. When matching with a genuine fingerprint, we do not want a low matching score. On the other hand, an impostor sample should not generate a high score. Therefore, it is necessary to control the number of considered pairs so that the genuine matching yields a high score while the impostor matching generates a low score. We set an *upper bound* and a *lower bound* to overcome this challenge with the hypothesis that a genuine sample possesses a high number of highly correlated Bag of Words meanwhile an impostor sample has a low number of similar Bag of Words. In short, these parameters are used to ensure that the number of considered pairs falls in the specified range.

The EMCC matching score between two fingerprint images is generated as follows:

$$S_{emcc} = W(n_p) * \Delta_{mod} \quad (4)$$

where:

$$\Delta_{mod} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{n_p} \Delta_i^2}{n_p} \quad (5)$$

On the other hand, $W(n_p)$ is a dynamic weight function of the number of chosen pairs n_p controlled by the parameter ρ . It is defined as:

$$W(n_p) = e^{-\rho * (\frac{1}{n_p} - 0.1)} \quad (6)$$

S_{emcc} is one of the three measures we will feed into the multi-layer matching module.

In the next section, we will present the second module that contributes to improving the performance of the fingerprint authentication system.

C. KNN Minutia Descriptor

Algorithm 2: Generate KNN Minutia Descriptor

Data: Minutiae set M , MPT parameters

Result: Transformed templates v

foreach Minutia m in set M **do**

 apply KNN clustering algorithm to form a local structure;

foreach minutia member in local structure **do**

 connect with the reference minutia m ;

 extract feature vector f ;

 apply quantization;

 apply MPT;

In our previous work [19], the KNN clustering algorithm was used to extract fingerprint features. In this paper, we improved the performance by expanding the idea of using the KNN to construct the so-called KNN Minutia Extractor with the help of the Multivariate Polynomial Transformation (MPT), which also functions as an irreversible transformation. In other words, MPT is not only used for protection but also to contribute to generating the minutia descriptor. An overview of this process is presented in the Algorithm 2.

1) *Raw Features Extraction*: On each minutia m in the set M , we apply the KNN to identify its k nearest neighbors where k is a predefined parameter. This process results in n clusters. For each pair constructed by connecting the reference minutia m to the member q of the cluster, the following features are extracted:

$$f = (l_{mq}, \alpha, \beta, t_q) \quad (7)$$

where:

- l_{mq} is the Euclidean distance between the reference minutia m and the member q .
- α is the angle formed by the reference minutia m 's orientation vector θ_m and the line that connects m and q .
- β is the angle formed by the member minutia q 's orientation vector θ_q and the line that connects m and q .
- t_q is the type of the member minutia q .

Fig. 3: Multi-layer Fingerprint Matching Algorithm: After all three measures have been generated and fed to the Matching module in the framework, the stored template data is retrieved from the database. A predefined measure is chosen to be compared first. If the similarity satisfies the threshold in the current filter, a "matched" decision is given. Otherwise, another measure is compared for the similarity in the next filter. This process repeats until either a measure satisfies its corresponding threshold or there are no more measures to compare with, leading the decision to be "non-matched."

After this process, each cluster is represented by F , a $k \times 4$ feature matrix. To compensate for the distortion that is caused by external factors when the fingerprint is scanned, a quantization is applied by choosing an appropriate step size for each individual feature, except the minutia type. The result of the quantization is a matrix F_b whose each row is a vector that contains three natural numbers and a bit, which respectively represent the level number of the quantized features and the type of the member minutia:

$$F_b = \{f_b\}_1^k \quad (8)$$

where each: $f_b = (b_l, b_\alpha, b_\beta, t)$.

2) *Multivariate Polynomial Transformation*: Irreversible transformations have mostly been relied on underdetermined system of linear equations. However, this approach has been proved to be vulnerable to the Attack via Record Multiplicity [23]. Therefore, we propose the non-linear Multivariate Polynomial Transformation (MPT) to utilize the power of non-linear system of polynomials to protect the raw fingerprint features. In [24], Courtois et al. claimed that solving large systems of quadratic multivariate polynomial equations is an NP-hard problem. In our case, we applied a higher-degree multivariate polynomial to increase the complexity of finding the solutions.

Given the vector $f_b = (b_l, b_\alpha, b_\beta, t)$ and a multivariate polynomial equation is generated with the form:

$$\sum_1^\mu \prod_1^\nu x_j^\chi = \zeta \quad (9)$$

where μ , ν are the number of monomials and the number of variables in each monomial, respectively. Both are predefined as positive integers. χ is the degree corresponding to variable x_j ; and x_j 's are the components of vector f_b .

Upon plugging in the variables and evaluating the equation, we yield the result ζ . Repeating this process 4 times (which

is also the number of components in each vector f_b) gives us the Multivariate Polynomial System of Equations:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \sum_1^{\mu_1} \prod_1^{\nu_1} x_{j_1}^{\chi_1} = \zeta_1 \\ \sum_1^{\mu_2} \prod_1^{\nu_2} x_{j_2}^{\chi_2} = \zeta_2 \\ \sum_1^{\mu_3} \prod_1^{\nu_3} x_{j_3}^{\chi_3} = \zeta_3 \\ \sum_1^{\mu_4} \prod_1^{\nu_4} x_{j_4}^{\chi_4} = \zeta_4 \end{array} \right. \quad (10)$$

This is a well-defined Multivariate Polynomial System of Equations and solving such system is an NP-hard problem. We can always enhance the security of the system by introducing more variables to the system. In other words, we can add more *virtual features* to each vector f in Eq. (7). In our case, we apply a hash function that takes the features as input. In details, each feature from a feature vector is fed into the hash function SHA224 to create 28 8-bit hash values. After all four features have been hashed, there are a total of 112 hash values, which are to be used as input for the MPT. However, this also increases the computation that needs to be done in order to perform matching. Therefore, the balance between the number of variables in an MPT and the time to perform matching is an optimization problem that depends on the power of the computer on which the framework is implemented. A hash function alone is not strong enough in this case due to the quantization of the input. Therefore, MPT can enhance the system's security.

All the ζ values obtained by evaluating all four polynomials are then translated into binary string and concatenated altogether. position-wisely. In addition, each ζ value will be given one extra bit to indicate its sign following the simple rule: If $\zeta \geq 0$, its sign bit is '1'. Otherwise, it is '0'. Note that all the sign bits are appended at the end of the string. The whole binary string is then translated back into a decimal number. This means that each cluster is now represented by:

$$F_T = \{f_T\}_1^k \quad (11)$$

where each f_T is now a decimal number.

At this stage, F_T is used to represent each minutia and will be stored in the database and will function as the template to be compared with.

3) *KNN Minutia Descriptor Similarity*: The normalized similarity between two descriptors: template v_T and v_Q KNN Minutia Descriptors is calculated as follows:

$$S(v_{Tp}, v_{Qr}) = 1 - \frac{|P(v_{Tp}) \setminus P(v_{Qr})| + |P(v_{Qr}) \setminus P(v_{Tp})|}{|v_{Tp}| + |v_{Qr}|} \quad (12)$$

where:

- $P(t)$ is a set function that converts KNN minutia descriptor data t into a set, meaning that no duplication is allowed.
- \setminus is the set difference operation.

After the similarity between all pairs has been calculated, we first rank them in a descending order. Scores with higher ranks are given higher weights. Our hypothesis is that if the query comes from the same finger as the template, more high scores are present. On the other hand, in case of a false-accept attack, a very low number of high scores are present. The formula to generate the KNN score S_{knn} is as follows:

$$S_{knn} = \sum_{i=1}^{k_p} S_i w_i \quad (13)$$

where:

- k_p is the number of considered pairs
- S_i is the score at rank i th
- w_i is the corresponding weight given for score at rank i th. Kindly note that all the weights sum to 1.0.

D. Multi-filter Fingerprint Matching Algorithm

As we have already extracted the features and calculated the similarity from both layers, we need to generate a fused matching score and make a decision: whether the query B is from the same fingerprint as the template A or it is only an impostor trying to gain unauthorized access.

1) *Fusion Similarity*: Eq. (6) is expanded to generate a fused score as follows:

$$S_{fused} = e^{-\lambda \left(\frac{1}{w_{emcc} S_{emcc} + w_{knn} S_{knn}} \right)} \quad (14)$$

This score will be fed to the decision-making module for the consideration along with other measures.

2) *Multi-filter Fingerprint Matching Algorithm*: Traditionally, a single fused score has been used for the matching decision. Although a fused score can take into account multiple different characteristics, the end result tends to be a trade-off score which can filter out some subtle discriminative characteristics of some instances. In order to address this issue, a multilayer-filtering algorithm is proposed as shown in Fig. 3. A multi-staged matching decision scheme that takes the EMCC similarity score, the KNN similarity score, and the fused score into consideration is designed in this framework to determine if two fingerprints come from the same finger.

In details, after the three measures have been generated, a predefined measure will be compared against the threshold T_1 . If it does not pass this threshold, the next measure is checked against the threshold T_2 ; If unsuccessful, the last measure is checked against the threshold T_3 . If none of the measures is successful, the decision will be "non-matched".

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULT

	KNN Descriptor		EMCC	
	Generate	Match	Generate	Match
FVC2002 DB1	2.82	0.34	0.33	1.47
FVC2002 DB2	3.94	0.63	0.47	3.18
FVC2002 DB3	1.12	0.09	0.27	1.05
FVC2004 DB2	1.24	0.13	0.30	1.33

TABLE I: Computation time in seconds

Table I shows the average computational cost for the EMCC and the KNN Descriptors. Two methods were implemented in Python 3.6 and run on the 6th generation Intel Core i7-6700 3.4Ghz with 16GB of RAM. As we can see the total time to generate a cancelable template for both measures is about 4 seconds, which is practically acceptable in the real-world application. With the KNN Descriptor, the maximum base and power of the operation are 6 and 28, respectively, which correspond to approximately 3 and 5 bits. Therefore, the calculations performed in an MPT are not exponential, which means that not much computational power is required. In addition, the program was not written in its most optimal manner. Hence, it can be tuned to use much less computational power. Importantly, the framework can be implemented in C with optimization techniques to achieve its best efficiency. In order to evaluate the accuracy of the framework, we implemented it with the four publicly available datasets: FVC2002 DB1, FVC2002 DB2, FVC2002 DB3, and FVC2004 DB2. Each dataset has 100 fingerprints, each of them possesses 8 different impressions. The image quality of the dataset ranks from very good to very poor, respectively. The parameters used in the paper are presented in Table II. Note that we only show the parameters introduced in this paper. The parameters from other papers are detailed in the original papers.

Both the traditional FVC and One versus One protocol were employed. In the FVC protocol, each impression of each fingerprint is chosen to be the template to be compared with all other samples that belong to the same finger to generate the False Rejection Rate (FRR), which is the framework's probability to falsely reject a fingerprint from the same finger. This means that there are totally 2800 genuine tests in each dataset for the FVC protocol. On the other hand, One versus One protocol uses the first impression to match against the second impression of each fingerprint to generate the FRR, leading to 100 genuine tests in each dataset. Both protocols use the first impression of each fingerprint to match against the first impression of other fingerprints for the impostor test. Hence, 4950 impostor tests are run to measure the False Acceptance Rate (FAR), which is the system's probability to mistakenly accept an impostor fingerprint. The performance of the framework is then measured by generating the Equal

Parameters	Descriptions	Value	
		1v1	FVC
Λ	Number of words in each bag	1280	
Φ	Number of words in each chunk	100 - 350	100, 300
d_R	Number of rows in Projection Matrix	1280	
ϵ	Chunk filtering threshold parameter	0.7 - 0.75	
ω_{bag}	Low Bag of Words similarity score filter	0.3 - 0.6	
n_P	Number of considered pairs in Eq. (5)	[4, 10]	
ρ	Parameter in (6)	6.6336	
k	Number of nearest neighbors used in KNN algorithm	5 - 11	
μ	Number of monomials in a polynomial equation	2 - 3	
ν	Number of variables in each monomial	1 - 112	
χ	Power of a variable	0 - 4	
k_p	The number of considered pairs in Eq. (13)	2	
w_i	Weight of the score at i th rank in Eq. (13)	0.55 - 0.7	
w_{emcc}	The weight of S_{emcc} in Eq. (14)	0.1 - 0.3	
w_{knn}	The weight of S_{knn} in Eq. (14)	0.9 - 0.7	
λ	The parameter of Eq. (14)	0.1 - 0.3	

TABLE II: Parameters used in the experiments

Error Rate (EER), which is the rate when the FRR and the FAR are equal.

Fig. 4: ROC for One versus One protocol

A. Lost Key Scenario

Lost Key Scenario is considered to be the worst case as the user loses his/her parameter key to the attacker. This means that the attacker can take this advantage to penetrate the authentication system. In order to simulate this scenario, we

use the same parameter key to generate the polynomials for all users in the KNN-MPT module. For the EMCC module, the same random projection matrix is used to evaluate the impostor performance in the lost key scenario. Since two methods are fused, we evaluated separate performances of the EMCC module and the KNN-MPT module, then compare them with the proposed fused method to show the effect in improving the performance. The separate performance results of the FVC protocol in terms of the EER are shown in Table. III. All variations of the matching algorithms are assessed and shown in Table IV. Bold text indicates the lowest EER. In addition, the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curves for all the datasets in One versus One protocol and the FVC protocol are shown in Fig.4 and Fig.6. The thresholds T1, T2, T3 varied based on the databases. In order to generate the ROC curves, two of the three thresholds will be fixed while the other is changing. The best EER is recorded and chosen to generate the ROC curves.

	FVC2002 DB1	FVC2002 DB2	FVC2002 DB3	FVC2004 DB2
EMCC	8.9	5.67	23.40	15.49
KNN	4.02	3.64	11.62	18.95

TABLE III: Standalone performance in EER

	FVC2002 DB1	FVC2002 DB2	FVC2002 DB3	FVC2004 DB2
EMCC - KNN - Fused	0.28	0.08	1.41	3.38
EMCC - Fused - KNN	0.28	0.08	1.40	3.45
KNN - EMCC - Fused	0.28	0.08	1.41	3.38
KNN - Fused - EMCC	0.38	0.23	1.43	3.83
Fused - EMCC - KNN	0.28	0.08	1.40	3.45
Fused - KNN - EMCC	0.42	0.23	1.43	3.83

TABLE IV: EERs (%) of different order in the matching algorithm

The resultant EER's of the proposed framework are presented and compared in Table V and Table VII.

	FVC2002 DB1	FVC2002 DB2	FVC2002 DB3	FVC2004 DB2
Ferrara et al. [25]	0	0.37	4.94	-
Jin et al. [26]	4.36	1.77	-	21.82
Wang and Hu [14]	3.5	5	7.5	-
Wang and Hu [15]	3	2	7	-
Wang et al. [16]	1	2	5.2	13.3
Wang et al. [17]	0.19	1	4.29	9.01
Tran et al. [19]	0.2	0.04	4.78	7.64
Kho et al [20]	0	0	2	4
PM (cancelable EMCC)	0	0	0.14	2.71

TABLE V: EER (%) Comparison in One vs. One Protocol

	FVC2002 DB1	FVC2002 DB2	FVC2002 DB3	FVC2004 DB2
EMCC	2.8634	3.2811	1.6117	2.0391
KNN-MPT	3.03	3.1912	2.1816	1.7644
Fused	4.0002	4.9040	2.8152	2.7037

TABLE VI: Decidability index d'

As we can see in these tables, the proposed framework shows the best performance in comparison with the other

state-of-art methods in the field. On the other hand, with the traditional FVC protocol, except the work proposed in [21], the proposed framework shows a superior performance when compared with the rest, even when dealing with the FVC2004 DB2, which has been considered to be a tough dataset due to the noise and distortion present in the fingerprint images. The reason for the slightly worse performance than the work in [21] is because Sadhya et al. [21] only conducted 1000 genuine tests in their experiments while we followed strictly the FVC protocol with 2800 tests. Hence, it is not comparable. Table VI shows the decidability index d' for each database using the standalone measure EMCC, KNN, or Fused. However, since our framework applies multiple thresholds to make a decision, these indices do not reflect fairly how separate the genuine and impostor distributions are in terms of matching decision. Thus, we conducted a more sophisticated decidability analysis.

B. Decidability Analysis

According to the original definition in [27], decidability index is used to evaluate the gap between the same samples' matching score distribution and impostor samples' matching score distribution. Therefore the whole database's d' has lost its interpretation. For illustration purpose, we choose a fingerprint and calculate the decidability index d' as follows: Each of the fingerprint's impressions is matched against the other impressions of the same fingerprint to build the genuine matching score distribution; the first impression of the fingerprint is matched against the first impression of other fingerprints to build the impostor matching score distribution. This protocol yields 28 genuine scores and 99 impostor scores for each measure: EMCC, KNN-MPT, and Fused measure. The matching algorithm being used in this experiment follows the order EMCC-KNN-Fused, meaning that the EMCC score will be compared against EMCC threshold first. If it passes this threshold, decision is made. If not, the KNN score is checked against a KNN threshold and the same process applies. If the pair comparison cannot pass any of the three layers, the query is considered as an impostor. We chose fingerprint 1 from FVC2002-DB1 as the subject for this experiment. The whole process is illustrated in Figure 5.

As we can see from the figures: After the first filter EMCC with threshold being set to 0.53, from the 28 genuine tests, 15 tests passed this filter while 13 failed. All of which were carried on to the second filter of KNN where 10 tests were correctly identified as genuine and three still failed. In the end, the last filter of the fused measure accepted these last three tests. On the other hand, all 99 impostor tests have been filtered out correctly with no single impostor has been falsely accepted by any of the three filters. The d' index progressively increases from 1.147 in the EMCC filter to 2.2712 in the KNN-MPT filter, and finally reached 5.8250 with the Fused filter. The very last d' index is of crucially important as it is the point where the framework decides to reject or not. In addition, as we can see from the graphs, the overlapped region between the genuine and impostor score distribution shrinks from the beginning to the end of the matching process. This analysis not only shows the uniqueness but also the

accuracy of this proposed framework. A unique advantage of our multi-layer matching decision framework is: a high threshold sufficiently far away from the overlapped region of the genuine and impostor score distributions could be used to make a "yes" decision in the first two stages. Therefore, a "yes" result tends to be highly reliable. For the instances that could not pass the high threshold will be passed to the next layer with different feature distributions where an additional information is introduced to aid the matching decision. Note that statistics in this one example is not reliable due to small population. However, it well illustrates the workings of our proposed framework.

	FVC2002 DB1	FVC2002 DB2	FVC2002 DB3	FVC2004 DB2
Ferrara et al. [25]	3.33	1.76	7.78	-
Das et al. [10]	4	-	-	-
Wang and Hu [15]	4	3	8.5	-
Kho et al. [20]	2.28	1.25	6.4	7
Jin et al. [28]	0.43	2.10	6.60	8.02
Abdullahi et al. [22]	0.364	0.538	2.395	5.925
PM (cancelable EMCC)	0.23	0.08	1.46	3.25

TABLE VII: EER (%) Comparison in FVC Protocol

C. Revocability and Diversity

Revocability and Diversity are what makes a cancelable template strong or not. In details, these characteristics of a cancelable template authentication system proves that templates generated by different parameter keys even from the same fingerprint should have no correlation. In order to evaluate our framework's ability to satisfy the revocability and the diversity, we follow the same practice as in [15] by using the FVC2002 DB2 and the following evaluation protocol. For each fingerprint, the first impression is chosen to generate 50 different transformed templates with 50 disparate parameters to compare with the original templates. This experiment was conducted for all measures: EMCC scores, KNN-MPT scores, and Fused scores. These are called *pseudo-impostor* test scores. The pseudo-impostor scores are then plotted together with genuine scores and impostor scores to compare the distribution as illustrated in Fig.7, Fig.8, and Fig.9 for the EMCC, the KNN-MPT, and the Fused measures, respectively. The pseudo-impostor score distribution should not have a significant overlapped region with the genuine score distribution. Looking at the figures, we can see that the genuine score distribution from all three measures is different from the pseudo-impostor score and the real impostor score distributions. The detailed statistics data is presented in Table VIII.

The Standard Deviation and Mean of each type of scores are presented. There is a big difference in terms of both Standard Deviation and Mean of genuine and impostor scores. On the contrary, the EMCC Pseudo-impostor score distribution's standard deviation and mean (0 and 0, respectively) are very close to the EMCC Impostor score distribution's counterpart (0.0538 and 0.0255, respectively). The same situation happens to KNN-MPT's and Fused's Pseudo Impostor and Impostor scores.

Fig. 5: All d' indices corresponding to the decision making process. If KNN filter is used first, the resultant EMCC's d' would drop to 0.4221

Fig. 6: ROC for FVC protocol

Fig. 7: Revocability Test with EMCC Measure

We can conclude that in the proposed framework, different keys generate different cancelable templates and that the attacker cannot perform a cross-template attack even if he or she is able to retrieve a cancelable template of the same finger with a different key. Therefore, the framework does satisfy the Revocability and Diversity condition.

	Std Dev	Mean
EMCC Genuine	0.4900	0.7995
KNN Genuine	0.1614	0.4740
Fused Genuine	0.0848	0.8017
EMCC Impostor	0.0538	0.0255
EMCC Pseudo Impostor	0	0
KNN Impostor	0.0933	0.3848
KNN Pseudo Impostor	0.0423	0.0232
Fused Impostor	0.0287	0.0391
Fused Pseudo Impostor	0.0024	0.0172

TABLE VIII: Standard Deviation and Mean of each score type

D. Unlinkability

1) *Unlinkability Analysis*: Unlinkability of a cancelable biometric template design measures the difference among transformed templates that originate from the same fingerprint. The framework in [29] proposed two linkability measures: Local Measure $D_{\leftrightarrow}(s)$ - System Score-Wise Linkability and Global Measure $D_{\leftrightarrow}^{sys}$ - System Overall Linkability. These two measures depend on the distributions of the probability $p(H_m|s)$ and $p(H_{nm}|s)$ of two templates belonging to mated or non-mated pair given a linkage score. In this test, we follow the protocol described in [29] to evaluate the $D_{\leftrightarrow}(s)$ and the $D_{\leftrightarrow}^{sys}$ for both the KNN-MPT module and the EMCC module. In details, for each module, six transformed databases are generated using six different keys. Mated score distribution is recorded by cross matching the images from the same biometric object. Non-mated score distribution is generated by collecting the scores from cross-matching different biometric object. The results for the KNN measure are plotted in Fig.10.

The mated and non-mated distributions in all four databases

Fig. 8: Revocability Test with KNN Minutia Descriptor Measure

Fig. 9: Revocability Test with Fused Measure

overlap the whole region. Besides, $D(s)$ is consistently 0 through the whole score distribution.

With the EMCC module, as we evaluated the mated and non-mated cross-matching, the score distribution consists of all 0's for both distributions without any variance. This means:

- The mated and non-mated score distribution both contain only score of 0, leading to the full unlinkability: $D_{\leftrightarrow}(s) = 0$.
- For scores other than 0, $p(H_m|s)$ and $p(H_{nm}|s)$ are undefined. Hence, $D_{\leftrightarrow}(s)$ does not exist when $s \neq 0$.
- For scores other than 0, $p(s|H_m)$ and $p(s|H_{nm})$ are undefined. Consequently, based on the mathematical definition in [29], $D_{\leftrightarrow}^{sys} = 0$.

We can conclude that the two measures KNN-MPT and EMCC both satisfy the unlinkability condition in this protocol.

2) *False Cross Match Rate (FCMR) and False Non-Cross Match Rate (FNCMR) Analysis:* According to [30], FCMR is defined as the probability of fingerprints generated from different fingers but are considered successful match while FNCMR refers to the probability of unsuccessfully matched pairs of fingerprints that come from a finger using different keys. These two measures are expected to sum approximately to 1 at all points (i.e.: $FCMR + FNCMR \approx 1$).

In order to measure the FCMR, in FVC2002 DB1, the transformed template of each of the fingerprints' first impression is matched against the first impression of other fingerprints in the database. With FNCMR, the transformed templates with different keys of the first and second impression of each fingerprint are matched. The result of this test is plotted and visualized in Fig. 11. It can be observed from this graph that at all points, the framework satisfies the condition $FCMR + FNCMR \approx 1$.

3) *Chunk Filtering Threshold Analysis:* As we evaluated the FCMR and FNCMR of this framework, we noticed that the chunk filtering threshold ϵ has an effect on the unlinkability of the templates. We performed different experiments by changing the value of ϵ . As we observe, with $\epsilon < 0.3$, S_{emcc} is all 1 for cross-matching. As a result, we have a uni-polar graph in which all the points lie at $FCMR = 1$ and $FNCMR = 0$. When $\epsilon \geq 0.3$, the generated graphs look similar to the one shown in Fig.11, which satisfied the condition $FCMR + FNCMR \approx 1$.

V. SECURITY ANALYSIS

A. Attack via Record Multiplicity (ARM)

ARM was first proposed in [31]. Given a raw biometric template x , multiple sets of parameters k_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$), and the transform function F , multiple transformed templates are generated as y_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$) where each transformation follows the one-time-pad model such that each individual y_i is infeasible to be linked back to x . For convenience, we will refer such transformation as the OTP model.

Being deployed in multiple locations, these y_i 's are not linked. However, assuming the OTP transformation function F and parameter set k_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$) are known, an adversary can launch the ARM if he/she can determine the original biometric data x through solving the acquired system of equations as shown in Eq.15. For example, a cancelable design with an OTP-based such as many-to-one linear mapping is exposed to the ARM [23] because a unique solution can be determined through solving a well-defined system of linear equations.

$$\begin{cases} y_1 = F(x, k_1) \\ y_2 = F(x, k_2) \\ y_3 = F(x, k_3) \\ \vdots \\ y_n = F(x, k_n) \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

With only the projection matrix R_P and the compromised transformed templates, an attacker can easily reverse the random projection matrix to get the original cell values C_m as this

Fig. 10: KNN-MPT's unlinkability analysis with all four databases

is an invertible operation in the context of an ARM. However, before getting to the C_{mP} , the attacker must compromise the encoding transformation. Unlike the binarization process introduced in the original MCC [5] which determines the bit value based on a fixed threshold, our encoding is based on the order of the two C_{mP} values in a word. Hence, even if the attacker collects massive amount of encoded data and uses statistics tools to get the distribution of the values, the attack will be unsuccessful since no information on the cell value is exposed after encoding. In details, two real numbers A and B will be encoded as $[1, 0]$ if $A > B$. Given $[1, 0]$, as the domain of A and B is dense, such encoding satisfies infinity-to-one mapping. It is similar in the case of $[0, 1]$ being given as the encoded word. Given $[1, 1]$ as the encoded word, the only leaked information is that $A = B$. It also satisfies infinite-to-one mapping. Hence, it is irreversible. Without further information about A and B, the probability of finding the true values of A and B is almost zero. Even when A and B are random but not uniformly distributed, the probability of

finding the true values of A and B is still negligible due to their dense domain. Therefore, this method is ARM-free.

For the KNN-MPT module, it has many possible solutions. In addition, since the system has as many equations as the number of variables, it is a well-behaved system. The attacker can use two tools to attack the system: Groebner basis or Newton-Raphson method.

When an attacker uses a Groebner basis-based solver to launch the attack onto the KNN-MPT module, the complexity could get to doubly exponential in the number of variables [32]. More details and analysis on the scenarios are presented in [33]. According to [34], given a well-defined Multivariate Polynomial System of Equations of n variables with degree of at most d , the arithmetic complexity to retrieve Groebner bases is $d^{O(n^2)}$. However, this is only the complexity to calculate Groebner bases of one system that associates with one feature vector f_b . The embedded hash function increases the number of variables for the MPT, leading to more complexity to solve the system of equations.

Fig. 11: FCMR and FNCMR when $\epsilon = 0.35$, KNN Descriptor Threshold and EMCC Threshold are set at 0.7 and 0.45, respectively.

On the other hand, Newton-Raphson method can also be used to estimate one of the solutions of the Multivariate Polynomial System of Equations. However, due to the nature of this method, several assumptions must be satisfied. One of the most important conditions is that the starting point must be chosen appropriately. Otherwise, the method might fail to converge or the solution returned is not the correct solution of the template. According to Bezout's theorem, given that d_1, d_2, d_3 , and d_4 are the degrees of each polynomial equation in the system, respectively, the system has at most $d_1 \cdot d_2 \cdot d_3 \cdot d_4$ solutions. This makes Newton-Raphson method hardly suitable to solve the Multivariate Polynomial System of Equations in our system because the solutions space grows exponentially and there is no suitable means to verify whether a guessed solution is the correct template solution.

The above analysis is the complexity upperbound without considering the hash function as well as the constraints of the variables. In practice, these variables are in limited range instead of the whole real field. It is unclear whether there exists a deterministic solution to the constrained Multivariate Polynomial Equations System.

B. Pre-image Attack

Pre-image attack refers to that: given an y , it is difficult to find an x such that $y = f(x)$.

EMCC module: Given the transformed templates, it is hard to find a systematical way in conducting the pre-image attack, including its approximated version, against the EMCC module. This is because of the combination of the random projection and the irreversible order-based encoding. To the best of our knowledge, there is no known closed-form mathematical solution available. For the feedback score guided solution search, please refer to our discussion on the hill-climb attack. For the input solution search without feedback score guidance, please refer to our discussion in the entropy analysis.

KNN-MPT module: Each local structure comprises of k minutiae, corresponding to k quantized feature vectors f_b 's. These quantized vectors are represented by a b bits. After transformation (hash+MPT), we rank the local structure similarity scores and construct a KNN-MPT score S_{knn} from the top ranked local structure similarity scores. Given the transformed templates, it is hard to find a systematical way in conducting the pre-image attack because the hash functionality embedded in the transformation has the pre-image resistant feature.

C. Hill-climb Attack

Hill-climb attack assumes that the similarity score is accessible by the adversary. As a result, modified templates of the biometric are iteratively fed into the recognition module until it is successful [35]. Each time, the attacker adjusts the input based on the retrieved similarity score from the previous trial to gradually approach the correct input, hence successfully gains access to the system. In the proposed framework, both the EMCC module and the KNN-MPT module show strong security against the hill-climb attack.

EMCC module: the attacker may obtain the binary representation of the transformed template, which is the result of the Irreversible Order-based Encoding. Given that the original encoded word is $[0, 1]$, other possible combinations of $[1, 0]$ or $[1, 1]$ may give a lower similarity. As a result, the attacker is able to identify the correct direction for further exploits. However, any further trials toward this direction do not reveal more information on how close the modified template is to the template stored in the database. In other words, the feedback from the similarity score does not provide any further information that helps the attacker modify the input. For example, given the two MCC values $C_{mP}(i, j, k) = 83.4$ and $C_{mP}(i', j', k') = 35.7$, the 2-bit encoded word constructed by the Irreversible Order-based Encoding is $w = [1, 0]$. Assume that the attacker launches a hill-climb attack by choosing $C'_{mP}(i, j, k) = 70$ and $C'_{mP}(i', j', k') = 90$. After some iterations, the attacker adjusts these values based on the retrieved similarity score and ends up with $C'_{mP}(i, j, k) = 80$ and $C'_{mP}(i', j', k') = 79$, which gives the correct encoded word $w' = [1, 0]$. However, once this point is reached, any further adjustments of $C'_{mP}(i, j, k)$ and $C'_{mP}(i', j', k')$ along this direction do not change the similarity score. Hence, the attacker is not able to exploit further from this direction. As far as these two elements are concerned, there is no way to identify better points if they have the same order relationship.

KNN-MPT module: the hash function not only helps increase the number of input variables to the MPT but also makes it harder for an adversary to launch a hill-climb attack. This is because the embedded hash function destroys the input/output relationship. Each pair of input/out is uncorrelated to one another. Hence, the previous trials do not help to find the better points.

Note that many optimization methods need information from previous trials in finding the next better points, which is similar to the principle of the hill-climb attack approach. Therefore, the advantages of our proposed KNN-MPT module and EMCC module are still useful against such attacks.

D. Entropy Analysis

Strictly speaking, entropy measures the probability of guessing the secret successfully. For convenience, we adopt the common practice with the uniform distribution assumption of the concerned variables. In this case, the analysis is about the brute-force search space.

EMCC module: There is no feature quantization in this module. Therefore, feature points are dense which implies the infinite entropy if the secret is about the exact original feature point. In this module, the error tolerance is achieved via the order encoding. In practical applications, approximated features can also break into the systems, especially when the matching threshold is small. It is very difficult to provide an accurate estimation of the system entropy in this situation if the secret includes the approximated feature. A coarse entropy estimation could be made by calculating the number of quantized feature points where the quantization takes the effect of the approximation into consideration. This is plausible but also challenging as it does not have quantization in this module. In order to simulate the effect of feature quantization, the following experiment is conducted. A random template X_0 is stored which is a bag of words. Then a matching experiment is performed against artificial templates, which are generated by perturbing X_0 by adding random values of δ to each of its elements. If the bound of δ is fixed and ten times of matching experiments do not change the matching score significantly for most of the artificial templates, the maximum magnitude of δ is used as the quantization step for all elements of the feature. Through this experiment, the bound of δ is determined as 0.2. This means that the quantization zone of each feature element is 0.4, leading to 2.5 disjoint quantization zones for each of the feature elements as the feature element value is normalized in the range [0,1]. For convenience, we just use two possible quantized values for each feature element. There are 1280 cells in a feature vector. Therefore, there are 2^{1280} distinct quantized feature points, leading to the entropy being 1280 bits.

KNN-MPT module: As mentioned above, each local structure in this module is represented by the k feature vectors. Each of them is quantized and represented by b bits. When the matching is performed, the number of involved local structure pairs LS is taken into consideration. Hence, the total number of entropy bits are given as: $E_b = b * k * LS$. In our experiment, each of the three features l , α , and β is represented by 5 bits. Adding the last bit that represents the minutia type, we have $b = 16$. In order to generate the KNN-MPT score S_{knn} , we first rank the local structure scores in descending order then choose the two pairs with the highest scores. Hence, LS is set at 2. The number of feature vectors k depends on the database.

The brute-force search space in terms of number of trials for each method is given in Table IX.

There is no doubt that any result from the theoretic security analysis tends to be conservative due to the simplified assumptions. In practice, the system's FAR is a more realistic indicator of the security strength. For example, the security strength against the pre-image attack, and a practical system's entropy will be bounded by the FAR performance. This is because the

	KNN Descrip- tor	EMCC
FVC2002 DB1	2^{320}	2^{1280}
FVC2002 DB2	2^{352}	2^{1280}
FVC2002 DB3	2^{192}	2^{1280}
FVC2004 DB2	2^{160}	2^{1280}

TABLE IX: Number of trials to attack each database with each method

FAR represents the false acceptance rate produced from the imposter attacks. It has included the effects of the matching threshold and the real biometrics distribution which a theoretic analysis is infeasible to consider. It is easy to achieve a very low FAR by increasing the matching threshold. However, it will also decrease the FRR performance at the same time. Therefore, the EER performance would be a fair indicator for measuring the security strength of a practical system as it provides the FAR performance with the balance of the FRR. Our system provides the best EER performance which should also provide a superior security strength in terms of entropy and resistance to the pre-image attack.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have proposed a novel dynamic multi-filtering framework that contains two layers of cancelable template designs. One of which is the KNN Minutia Descriptor that is equipped with the Multivariate Polynomial Transformation which relies on the power of the Multivariate Polynomial Equations System. The other is the Enhanced version of the Minutia Cylinder Code which is protected by an Irreversible Order-based Encoding transformation. A multi-layer fingerprint matching scheme is also proposed so that the decision making process no longer depends wholly on a single threshold. The proposed framework shows competitive matching performance in four public datasets in comparison with other state-of-art methods in the field. In addition, our system has the capability to defend against the well-known Attack via Record Multiplicity as well as is resistant against the pre-image attacks and the hill-climb attacks. While it is true that the multi-layer matching algorithm will provide more chance instead of one for the imposter to pass the system, our innovative system can effectively mitigate such risk. Our multi-layer matching algorithm is about choosing the most distinguishable genuine-imposter distribution response (between the KNN-MPT module and the EMCC module) of the sample for the decision where the matching threshold could be set relatively high above the genuine-imposter distribution overlapped region to reduce the risk of accepting the imposter. This is supported by our excellent EER system performance. The source code of this framework is available on request via email: j.hu@adfa.edu.au.

There is still a room for further improvement. The distribution of the cell values contributes to the performance of the EMCC: If we can determine this distribution and utilize it for improving the matching score, the EER performance is expected to be better. On the other hand, various clustering techniques can be used to cluster the minutiae on a fingerprint image. An appropriate clustering algorithm will retain the

topology of the cluster according to minutiae distribution of the individual image. Therefore, the performance could be improved by carefully choosing the cluster algorithm. These are interesting directions for our future work.

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